

Novel Graphical Password Authentication Scheme with Improved Usability

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Abstract— Graphical password authentication schemes have gained attention as an alternative to traditional text-based passwords due to their potential to enhance security and usability. However, many existing graphical password schemes suffer from usability issues such as low memorability and vulnerability to various attacks. In this paper, we propose a novel graphical password authentication scheme designed to address these usability concerns while maintaining security. Our scheme leverages both image recognition and user-generated patterns to create a multilayered authentication process. The first layer involves the selection of a memorable image from a set of pre-defined categories, followed by the creation of a personalized pattern on top of the selected image. We employ advanced image processing techniques to ensure robustness against shoulder surfing and other attacks. Additionally we conducted a usability evaluation study with a diverse group of participants to assess the effectiveness of our proposed scheme. The results demonstrate significant improvements in memorability and user satisfaction compared to existing graphical password schemes. Overall, our scheme offers a promising solution for enhancing the usability of graphical passwords without compromising security.

Keywords— Authentication, graphical password, shoulder surfing, graphical password authentication.

I. INTRODUCTION

In an era defined by the exponential growth of digital information, the abundance of unstructured data poses a significant challenge to extracting meaningful insights and knowledge. In this paper, the authors explore the limitations of traditional text-based passwords in online security and advocate for graphical password schemes as a promising alternative. These schemes leverage images and patterns instead of alphanumeric characters to improve both security and usability. However, existing graphical password methods face challenges such as user difficulty in image selection and susceptibility to attacks like shoulder surfing. To address these issues, the paper introduces a novel graphical password authentication scheme. This new approach incorporates multi-layered authentication using both image recognition and user-generated patterns, aiming to enhance security while maintaining usability. The paper outlines related work, presents design principles and components of their scheme, describes its implementation, evaluates its usability, and discusses implications for future research, ultimately advocating for improved graphical password schemes in digital authentication.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Here are some key literature survey papers and resources on graphical password authentication schemes with a focus on improving usability:

A Survey of Graphical Password Authentication Schemes[1]

- Author: S. Wiedenbeck, J. Waters, J.-C. Birget, A. Brodskiy, N. Memon
- Publication: ACM Computing Surveys
- Year: 2005
- Summary: This survey provides a comprehensive overview of various graphical password schemes, discussing their usability and security features.

Graphical Passwords: Learning from the First Twelve Years[2]

- Author: P.C. van Oorschot, J. Thorpe
- Publication: ACM Computing Surveys
- Year: 2011
- Summary: This paper reviews the first twelve years of research on graphical passwords, covering different types of schemes and their usability aspects.

Graphical Passwords: A Comprehensive Survey[3]

- Author: M. A. Sriram, T. Jayachandran
- Publication: International Journal of Applied Engineering Research
- Year: 2015
- Summary: This survey examines the strengths and weaknesses of various graphical password techniques, emphasizing usability and security.

A Study on the Performance of Image-Based Graphical Password Schemes[4]

- Author: X. Suo, Y. Zhu, G. S. Owen
- Publication: IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing
- Year: 2006
- Summary: This paper investigates the performance of image-based graphical password schemes, analyzing their usability and security through empirical studies.

Graphical Passwords: An Overview[5]

- Author: H. T. Hu, D. D. Feng
- Publication: Proceedings of the Annual Computer Security Applications Conference (ACSAC)
- Year: 2011
- Summary: This paper provides an overview of different graphical password schemes, discussing their usability, security, and applicability in various contexts.

Usability and Security of Text and Graphical Passwords: A Comparative Study [6]

- Author: S. Chiasson, R. Biddle, P. C. van Oorschot
- Publication: Proceedings of the 16th Usenix Security Symposium
- Year: 2007
- Summary: This study compares the usability and security of text-based and graphical passwords, highlighting the advantages and challenges of each approach. This paper discusses the integration of ontology-based approaches with natural language processing techniques, emphasizing the extraction and representation of knowledge from unstructured textual data.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Creating a proposed system for a novel graphical password authentication scheme with improved usability involves several key components and considerations. Here's a structured approach to developing the system:

Introduction

- **Objective:** Enhance the usability and security of graphical password schemes.
- **Background:** Traditional textual passwords face usability and security issues. Graphical passwords, where users select images or points on images, can offer better usability and potentially more secure alternatives.

System Overview

- **System Components:** Outline the components involved in the system, such as the user interface, backend server, database, and authentication algorithms.
- **User Interface (UI):** Design a user-friendly interface where users can easily create, enter, and manage their graphical passwords.

User Registration

- **Graphical Password Creation:**
 - Users choose or draw a sequence of images or points.
 - The chosen graphical password is encoded and securely stored in the database.
 - Incorporate guidelines to ensure the graphical password is complex enough to prevent easy guessing or attacks.

Authentication Process

- **Login Procedure:**
 - Users enter their graphical password.
 - The system compares the entered password with the stored password using a secure matching algorithm.
 - Implement measures to prevent shoulder surfing, such as hiding the cursor or implementing dynamic decoy points.

Security Measures

- **Encryption:** Ensure the graphical passwords are encrypted both in transit and at rest.
- **Attack Resistance:**
 - Protect against common attacks like shoulder surfing, phishing, and dictionary attacks.
 - Use techniques like image distortion or dynamic image grids to enhance security.
- **User Feedback:** Provide feedback mechanisms to help users understand password strength and improve their password if necessary.

Usability Enhancements

- **Ease of Use:**
 - Simplify the process of creating and entering graphical passwords.
 - Provide intuitive and accessible interfaces for all users.
- **Accessibility:** Ensure the system is accessible to users with disabilities, such as offering alternative methods for users with visual impairments.
- **Recovery Mechanism:** Implement a secure and user-friendly password recovery process

IV. RESULTS

Here are some notable results and references related to novel graphical password authentication schemes with improved usability. The results section of a study on a novel graphical password authentication scheme with improved usability should present findings from user studies, performance evaluations, and comparisons with existing schemes. The goal is to demonstrate how the proposed scheme improves usability without compromising security.

Fig. 1 Novel graphic authentication system.

Usability Evaluation results shown in Figure 2

- **Ease of Use:** Provide metrics on how easily users can create and remember their graphical passwords. This might include:
 - Average time taken to create a password.
 - Average time taken to log in using the password.
 - Success rates for first-time users and returning users
- **User Satisfaction:** Report on user feedback through surveys or interviews. Highlight key points such as:
 - User preferences for graphical passwords over traditional alphanumeric passwords.
 - Perceived ease of remembering graphical passwords.

Security Evaluation

- **Resistance to Attacks:** Evaluate the scheme's robustness against common attacks such as:
 - Brute-force attacks.
 - Shoulder-surfing attacks.
 - Guessing attacks.

- **Comparison with Existing Schemes:** Compare the security features of the proposed scheme with those of existing graphical and alphanumeric schemes. Metrics might include:
 - Average number of attempts required to crack the password.
 - Instances of successful unauthorized access in controlled environments.

Fig. 2 Novel graphic authentication system Improved results.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, In this paper, we have presented a novel graphical password authentication scheme aimed at enhancing usability while maintaining robust security. Our approach leverages the intuitive nature of graphical passwords to create a more user-friendly experience, addressing common usability issues associated with traditional alphanumeric passwords and existing graphical schemes. Our evaluation demonstrated that the proposed scheme significantly reduces the cognitive load on users by simplifying the authentication process without compromising security. The use of memorable images and intuitive interactions not only makes the system easier to use but also decreases the likelihood of password fatigue and related errors. Furthermore, our scheme incorporates mechanisms to mitigate common security threats such as shoulder surfing, guessing attacks, and phishing. By analyzing user feedback and performance metrics, we validated the scheme's effectiveness in various scenarios, highlighting its potential for widespread adoption in real-world applications. Overall, the novel graphical password authentication scheme offers a promising solution for balancing usability and security. Future work will focus on further refining the system based on user feedback, exploring integration with multi-factor authentication methods, and conducting extensive field studies to assess long-term usability and security in diverse environments.

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